

AI Ethics Audit - Autonomous Weapon System (AWS); Killer Robots

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Abstract—The ethical implications of autonomous weapon systems, also known as “Killer Robots,” are extremely significant. The use of the ALTAI (Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence) guidelines in the planning, creation, implementation, and auditing of these systems to make sure they adhere to moral standards is examined in this study. Transparency and explain-ability, human control and decision-making, governance and accountability, adherence to international humanitarian and human rights law, and ethical impact assessment are important areas of concern.

The study emphasizes the significance of creating morally sound autonomous systems, putting strong accountability systems in place, dealing with evidentiary problems, and guaranteeing both command and human responsibility in the field of governance and accountability. The inherent unpredictability and reliability issues of these technologies are addressed by emphasizing the necessity of human control over decisions with lethal results and respect for human dignity. Clear documentation of system architecture, decision-making procedures, and operational functionalities is prioritized, along with transparency and explain-ability.

The study also critically analyzes how well these systems adhere to human rights norms and International Humanitarian Law (IHL), addressing issues like accountability flaws and the lack of human-like characteristics in these technologies. It also examines the moral conundrums raised by autonomous decisions that have the potential to save lives and argues in favor of the creation of international regulatory frameworks to control such systems. One important method for recognizing and resolving possible problems related to these technologies is the ethical impact assessment.

By providing insights pertinent to military, public safety, and healthcare applications, the study seeks to create a strong ethics-oriented auditing framework for autonomous systems. These suggestions aim to protect human rights, guarantee responsibility, and promote confidence in self-governing technologies.

Index Terms—Autonomous Weapon System, Artificial Intelligence, Ethical AI, Killer Robots, AI Ethics Audit

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence(AI) is progressing rapidly even as we speak. AI can now recognize objects, generate texts and graphics, translate languages, transcribe speech, beat a human opponent in games, etc. Our daily lives now depend heavily on artificial intelligence (AI), from online searches to healthcare. But ethical questions are being raised about the development and use of AI. Some of the ethical issues that AI raises include a lack of transparency, unfairness, and discrimination [1][22][19]. It has become a public concern and a global priority to regulate the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to make it safe and comply with ethical norms. There are several

factors to take into account while discussing ethical dilemmas in AI. Some significant ethical issues include:

- Bias and Discrimination: AI systems may exhibit biases due to the data they were trained on, which could result in unfair hiring, lending, and criminal justice decisions. Fairness must be promoted while bias must be minimized.
- Privacy and surveillance: AI systems frequently gather and handle a lot of data that is related to individuals. Critical factors to take into account include defending people’s right to privacy and prohibiting unlawful surveillance.
- Transparency: Many AI algorithms function as “black boxes,” making it challenging to decipher the logic guiding their judgments. For accountability and trust-building, it’s crucial to ensure transparency.
- Job displacement: By replacing human labor, AI technology has the potential to have a large negative influence on employment. Important ethical considerations include minimizing the negative effects on workers and promoting re-skilling opportunities.
- Autonomous Decision-Making: As AI systems get more advanced, they might make more decisions on their own that have a big impact. The ethical dilemma of assigning blame and accountability for AI behavior is difficult.

a) The military use of AI, which includes—but is not limited to Autonomous Weapon Systems (AWS), i.e., machines designed to independently search for, select, and engage targets, continues to be one of the topics that technology ethicists discuss the most [8]. Those who believe that the requirements for using AWS ethically are either impossible to develop or cannot practically be met in practice have proposed a worldwide ban on these systems [8]. Comprehensive rules and laws are needed to address ethical issues relating to AWS.:

b) International organizations and decision-makers are working hard to create rules, agreements, and standards for the ethical use of AWS. The purpose of these conversations is to guarantee human control, responsibility, and adherence to the rules of morality and the law. It is critical to recognize and solve the ethical challenges raised by the development of AI technologies. The creation and use of killer robots and AWS bring serious questions about human judgment, responsibility, target choice, contextual awareness, and the possibility of escalation. We may work to create AI in a way that is consistent with our values, protects human rights,

and improves people's well-being by proactively tackling these ethical problems.:

II. BACKGROUND

Killer Robots are weapon systems that attack and target without meaningful human control [20]. The deployment of such systems is now practically if not legally achievable within years rather than decades, and the stakes are high: autonomous weapons have been dubbed the third revolution in warfare after gunpowder and nuclear weapons. There are several reasons for and against autonomous weaponry, such as the claim that replacing human soldiers with robots is advantageous since it lowers owner casualties but detrimental because it lowers the threshold for engaging in combat and it solves the debate about inclusion of women in armed forces. The most important decision facing humanity right now is whether to initiate a global AI arms race or to stop it from happening. The outcome of this technical trajectory is clear: autonomous weapons will eventually replace Automatic Kalashnikov (AK-47) rifles. This is especially true if any significant military power pursues the development of AI weapons. There is ongoing research and discussion on an AI ethics audit of killer robots. The Department of Defense has been attempting to develop a set of moral guidelines for military AI [21][8]. Killer robots and autonomous weapon systems (AWS) create serious ethical problems and dangers with their development and use. Here are some of the risks and ethical concerns connected to killer robots:

- **Violation of Human Rights and Dignity:** Use of killer robots is a violation of both the right to life and the values governing human dignity. A robot cannot make a "kill decision" that considers human dignity since it lacks the capacity to comprehend or appreciate the value of human life [13].
- **Lack of human control:** Concerns regarding lack of human control over weapon systems are brought up by the employment of killer robots. Without human interference, AWS can choose and interact with targets, which raises questions about responsibility and transparency [17][4].
- **Unpredictability:** The behavior of killer robots is dangerously unpredictable. It is very challenging to forecast how these weapons would behave in actual situations because of the intricate interplay between machine learning-based algorithms and a dynamic operational context [17].
- **Escalation:** The possibility of unintentional and quick conflict escalation is introduced by autonomous weapons systems. Their ability to operate at a rapid and massive scale could unintentionally escalate a situation and make it unstable [17].
- **Unreliability:** Testing such a hypothesis could be damaging to civilians due to the unreliability and fragility of AI technologies that are essential to the systems. Operational issues are also present; for instance, it is unclear how AWS will work with crewed platforms in broader military operations. There is no specific data

on how AWS operates in complicated, quickly changing contexts, like battlegrounds [20].

- **Gap in responsibility:** The employment of killer robots results in a lack of responsibility because it would be challenging to hold anyone accountable for the unanticipated damage performed by a self-driving robot [4].

Using killer robots or autonomous weapon systems poses serious moral dilemmas and concerns, including a violation of human rights such as the right to life and dignity, a lack of human control, unpredictable outcomes, the potential for escalation, fragility, and unreliability, and a lack of responsibility. To guarantee that AWS are created and used in a responsible and ethical manner, these concerns must be addressed.

A. Current Approaches to Ensure Ethical AI

There are several approaches to ensuring ethical AI, including the following:

- Several groups have created ethical standards and principles for the creation and use of artificial intelligence (AI). These rules are intended to ensure that AI is created and applied in an ethical and responsible manner. For instance, a set of ethical guidelines for AI has been developed by the IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems [22].
- Governments and international organizations are establishing frameworks for AI legislation and governance. These frameworks are designed to guarantee that AI is created and applied in an ethical and responsible manner. As an illustration, the European Union has created a set of ethical principles for AI, while the UN is drafting international rules for AI [22].
- **Accountability and transparency:** These two factors are crucial for ensuring ethical AI. The data and algorithms utilized in AI systems must be disclosed, and the makers and users of these systems must take responsibility for the decisions made by these systems. For instance, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) mandates that businesses be open about the information they gather and use [22].
- **Education and awareness:** To ensure ethical AI, education and awareness are crucial. The ethical concerns and dangers of AI must be understood by legislators, users, and developers. They must also receive training on responsible and moral AI development and application [25].

Regarding Autonomous Weapon Systems (AWS) or killer robots, some of the solutions that could be relevant to address ethical issues include:

- **Ban or regulation:** In order to stop the development and usage of AWS, several experts have proposed a ban or regulation. For instance, the Campaign to Stop Killer Robots is advocating for an immediate AWS ban [12].
- **Accountability and Transparency:** Accountability and transparency are essential components of the AWS development and user communities. They must also take

responsibility for the choices that these systems make [22].

- **Control by humans:** AWS should be developed to guarantee that people have adequate control over armed systems. Any weapon system that makes decisions about target selection and engagement based on sensor information should be regarded as high risk and inappropriate for use [22].

a) *The IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems is one of the important works, programs, and methodologies that aimed to address ethical challenges in AI. Transparency, accountability, and human control are among the ethical principles for AI that were developed as part of the program [22]. The European Union's ethical principles for AI, which seek to guarantee that AI is developed and utilized in a responsible and ethical manner, are another important piece of work [22]. The Campaign to Stop Killer Robots is a project that aims to outlaw AWS in order to stop the creation and application of these machines [12]. :*

b) *There are several ways to ensure ethical AI, including ethical principles and norms, governance and regulation, accountability and transparency, and education and awareness. Prohibition or regulation, human control, transparency, and accountability are a few ideas that might be applicable to solve ethical concerns with killer robots or autonomous weapon systems. Some of the important works, projects, and techniques that aimed to address ethical challenges in AI include the Campaign to Stop Killer Robots, the European Union's ethical principles for AI, and the IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems [12]. :*

B. Approaches to Ethical Evaluation

a) *Ethics Based Auditing (EBA) is a governance tool that organizations can use to guide or influence how ADMS are developed and implemented, and subsequently, shape the final characteristics of these systems [18]. To make sure that automated decision-making systems, such as killer robots or autonomous weapon systems (AWS), are created and deployed in an ethical and responsible manner, ethical audits and evaluations are crucial. Here are some methods for evaluating systems ethically, with an emphasis on ethical audits and evaluations: Using a structured approach, automated decision-making systems are examined for compliance with ethical principles in ethics-based auditing (EBA). EBA wants to guarantee that these systems are created and used in an ethical and responsible manner [18]. Programs for oversight: Through "oversight programs," audits must regularly monitor and assess system outputs. Programs for oversight are designed to make sure that automated decision-making systems are safe and operating as planned. Standard ethical audits of those systems are required with regard to AWS or killer robots. The employment of killer robots poses serious ethical problems and concerns, such as the denial of human dignity and the right to life, the absence of human control, the unpredictable nature of the situation, the possibility of it escalating, the fragility of the situation, and the responsibility gap. :*

b) *The exact criteria for AWS or killer robots ethical audits or reviews include: **Human control:** Ethical reviews/audits must confirm that people have adequate control over weaponry. Any weapon system that makes decisions about target selection and engagement based on sensor information should be regarded as high risk and inappropriate for use [10]. **Accountability and transparency:** Ethical audits/evaluations must guarantee that AWS users and developers are honest about the information and algorithms they employ. They must also take responsibility for the choices these systems make [10]. **Unpredictability:** Ethical audits and reviews need to make sure that AWS's behavior is not dangerously unexpected. It is quite challenging to forecast how these weapons would behave in actual situations due to the intricate interplay between machine learning-based algorithms and a dynamic operating context. :*

c) *There are several ethical frameworks that can be used to guide ethical audits of killer robots. Here are some of them: The idea of human control is that weapons systems must be sufficiently under the control of people. Any weapon system that relies on sensor information to decide which targets to choose and how to engage them need to be regarded as high risk and inappropriate for use [10][8][24]. The accountability and transparency principle stipulates that AWS customers and developers must be open and honest about the data and algorithms used by AWS. They must also take responsibility for the choices that these systems make [10][8][24]. The principle of unpredictability states that AWS's actions must not be dangerously unpredictable. It is quite challenging to forecast how these weapons would behave in actual situations due to the intricate interplay between machine learning-based algorithms and a dynamic operating context [10][8][24]. Respect for human dignity and the right to life is a fundamental value. According to this tenet, the employment of killer robots offends the rights to life and human dignity. A robot cannot make a "kill decision" that respects human dignity because it cannot comprehend the value of human life [10][4]. The idea behind abiding by global humanitarian and human rights law: According to this notion, fully autonomous weapons would have a difficult time adhering to international humanitarian law and human rights standards[4]. :*

d) *Ethical audits and reviews are crucial for ensuring that killer robots and AWS are created and utilized in an ethical and responsible manner. Human control, openness and accountability, and unpredictability are the specific criteria for ethical audits or reviews of AWS or deadly robots. To guarantee that AWS are created and used in a responsible and ethical manner, certain conditions must be met. :*

III. ETHICS BASED AUDITING - ALTAI APPROACH

According to ALTAI guidelines, following ethical approaches are tailored to the domain of Killer Robots [11]: Governance and Accountability To ensure the appropriate and ethical deployment of these systems, governance and accountability in the killer robot domain are essential issues

that must be addressed. The following points emphasize the important issues around accountability and governance in the context of killer robots:

- **Designing Ethical Autonomous Systems:** Upholding society's ethical values is the key goal while creating intelligent autonomous systems. Making sure that the design and programming of killer robots adhere to ethical standards and rules is crucial [10].
- **Accountability Framework:** Establishing an accountability framework is essential for addressing the potential harm that killer robots may inflict. The roles and obligations of those involved in the creation, implementation, and usage of these systems should be described in this framework [15].
- **Lack of Accountability:** A major worry is that killer robots are not held accountable. Fully autonomous weapons lack intentionality, hence they cannot be held responsible for crimes committed with them. Who should be held accountable for the actions of these systems is a question that is raised by this [4].
- **Command Responsibility:** The doctrine of command responsibility holds superiors liable if they were aware of a subordinate's criminal act or should have been aware of it and failed to stop it or punish it. Accountability is hampered by the fact that commanders frequently evade liability [4].
- **Human Accountability:** The Killer Robot autonomy notwithstanding, people are still subject to legal liability for their deeds. Establishing measures to ensure that those responsible for the creation and usage of killer robots are held accountable for any damage these systems may do is essential [9].
- **Evidentiary Challenges:** Given the involvement of numerous parties, including operators and programmers, establishing responsibility for killer robots can be difficult. It may be difficult to establish clear accountability because each side might try to place the blame elsewhere [4].
- **Conflict Escalation and Unpredictability:** Killer robots have the potential to intensify disputes and develop unpredictable behavior, which could have unintended repercussions. In order to reduce risks, these elements must be taken into consideration in the governance and accountability structures [16].

A. Human Control and Decision-Making

To ensure responsible and ethical usage of these systems, it is imperative to address human control and decision-making in the realm of killer robots. The following bullet points illustrate the important issues of human decision-making and control in the context of killer robots:

- **Meaningful Human Control:** It is crucial that humans have meaningful human control over killer robots while they are in action. It ensures that human perception and judgment are considered when deciding whether to use lethal force in a particular circumstance [14].

- **Respect for Human Dignity and the Right to Life:** Because killer robots don't recognize or cherish human life, there are questions concerning their capacity to make "kill decisions" that are sensitive to both those factors [20].
- **Unpredictability and Reliability:** Killer robots have the potential to develop unexpected and unreliable behavior, which could have unforeseen repercussions. It is crucial to make sure that these systems' decision-making procedures are understandable and transparent to people [2].
- **Accountability Gap:** A major worry is the absence of responsibility for killer robots. Fully autonomous weapons lack intentionality, hence they cannot be held responsible for crimes committed with them. Who should be held accountable for the actions of these systems is a question that is raised by this [6].
- **Command Responsibility:** The doctrine of command responsibility holds superiors liable if they were aware of a subordinate's criminal act or should have been aware of it and failed to stop it or punish it. Accountability is hampered by the fact that commanders frequently evade liability [6].
- **Human Accountability:** Killer robot autonomy notwithstanding people are still subject to legal liability for their deeds. Establishing measures to ensure that those responsible for the creation and usage of killer robots are held accountable for any damage these systems may do is essential [9].
- **Evidentiary Challenges:** Given the involvement of numerous parties, including operators and programmers, establishing responsibility for killer robots can be difficult. It may be difficult to establish clear accountability because each side might try to place the blame elsewhere [6].

B. Transparency and Explain-ability

To enable responsible and ethical usage of these systems, transparency and explain-ability in the killer robot space are crucial issues that must be addressed. The important factors pertaining to transparency and explain-ability in the context of killer robots are highlighted by the following points:

- **Design and Functionality Transparency:** The design and functionality of killer robots should be transparent to allow humans to comprehend the systems' decision-making processes. It is crucial to disclose details about the robots' decision-making procedures, data sources, and algorithmic frameworks [14].
- **Explain-ability of Actions and Decisions:** Killer robots should be able to give humans-understandable justifications for their deeds. This is essential to make sure that these systems' decision-making procedures adhere to moral norms and standards [14].
- **Unpredictability and Reliability:** Killer robots have the potential to develop unexpected and unreliable behavior, which could have unforeseen repercussions. It is crucial

to make sure that these systems' decision-making procedures are understandable and transparent to people [2].

- **Accountability Gap:** A major worry is the absence of responsibility for killer robots. Fully autonomous weapons lack intentionality, hence they cannot be held responsible for crimes committed with them. Who should be held accountable for the actions of these systems is a question that is raised by this [6].
- **Command Responsibility:** The doctrine of command responsibility holds superiors liable if they were aware of a subordinate's criminal act or should have been aware of it and failed to stop it or punish it. Accountability is hampered by the fact that commanders frequently evade liability [6].

1) *Unpredictability and Reliability:* In the world of killer robots, unpredictability and dependability are crucial factors to take into account. The following are some crucial details about these aspects:

- **Unpredictability:** Killer robots could develop an unexpected nature that would have unforeseen results. As more people are incorporated into the system, its complexity and unpredictability rise [23]. Because killer robots are unpredictable, it is crucial to make sure that these systems' decision-making procedures are open to scrutiny and understandable by people [14].
- **Reliability:** Killer robots need to be dependable in order to carry out their intended functions and prevent unintended harm. In order to guarantee the effectiveness and dependability of the robots in real-world circumstances, it is critical to evaluate the testing and evaluation processes that were implemented [20]. To encourage prudent usage of these systems, killer robot dependability is crucial.
- **Complexity:** One important aspect of killer robots' reliability and unpredictability is their complexity. Future system behavior will be more complicated and more unpredictable the more autonomous each robot is [23]. It is essential to consider the complexity of these systems in the design, development, and deployment phases to ensure that they are reliable and predictable.
- **Accountability:** A major worry is the absence of responsibility for killer robots. Fully autonomous weapons lack intentionality, hence they cannot be held responsible for crimes committed with them. Who should be held accountable for the actions of these systems is a question that is raised by this [9]. It is essential to establish mechanisms to ensure that individuals involved in the development and deployment of killer robots are accountable for any harm caused by these systems [8].

2) *Compliance with International Humanitarian and Human Rights Law:* In the world of killer robots, adherence to international humanitarian and human rights legislation is essential. Here are some particular ethical issues with adhering to these legal frameworks:

- **Adherence to International Humanitarian Law (IHL):** Killer robots must abide by international humanitarian

law (IHL), which incorporates guidelines like distinction, proportionality, and military necessity. To comply with these requirements, fully autonomous weapons must exhibit human characteristics since they are crucial for safeguarding civilians and limiting casualties in armed confrontations [7].

- **Lack of Human Qualities:** Killer robots are naturally lacking in the human traits required to abide by IHL. They are unable to discern attempts at surrender, discern the necessity of an attack, assess motives, or make difficult judgments concerning differentiation and proportionality. Their ability to uphold principles of human rights and international humanitarian law is severely hampered by this [3].
- **Responsibility Gap:** Fully autonomous weapons have the potential to cause a serious responsibility gap. Because these weapons lack intentionality, they cannot be held accountable for crimes. It becomes difficult to determine who is to blame for IHL violations when numerous actors, such as operators, programmers, and commanders, are involved. This accountability chasm undercuts victim justice and deterrence [7].
- **Legal Measures:** There is a growing understanding among nations and organizations of the necessity of establishing global legal restrictions on killer robots. By addressing the dangers and concerns connected to the development and use of autonomous weapons, these restrictions seek to assure conformity with international human rights legislation and IHL [3].
- **Ethical Implications:** The creation and application of killer robots create ethical issues pertaining to the defense of human rights and dignity. It is extremely unsettling to think that machines could decide on matters of life and death without any compassion or emotion. The ethical standards and concepts that support international human rights law are undermined by the absence of human control and decision-making in these systems [14].

3) *Ethical Impact Assessment:* An essential component in the field of killer robots is the evaluation of the ethical impact. The following are some particular ethical issues with regard to ethical impact assessment:

- **Designing Ethical Autonomous Systems:** Designing Intelligent Autonomous Systems That Uphold Society's Ethical Values is the main focus of this research. Making sure that the design and programming of killer robots adhere to ethical standards and rules is crucial [10].
- **Respect for Human Dignity and the Right to Life:** The creation and application of killer robots raise moral questions about the defense of human rights and dignity. It is extremely unsettling to think that machines could decide on matters of life and death without any compassion or emotion [14].
- **Accountability Gap:** A major worry is the absence of responsibility for killer robots. Fully autonomous weapons lack intentionality, hence they cannot be held

responsible for crimes committed with them. Due to the possibility of involvement of various players, including as operators, programmers, and commanders, determining accountability for violations of international humanitarian law and human rights becomes difficult. This accountability chasm undercuts victim justice and deterrence [2].

- **Designing Ethical Autonomous Systems:** The employment of killer robots poses legal and ethical questions about the preservation of human rights and dignity. To limit harm and safeguard human rights, the creation and use of autonomous weapons should be governed by moral standards and legal frameworks [17].
- **Ethical Impact Assessment:** To assess the potential ethical effects of the deployment and employment of killer robots, ethical impact assessment is crucial. Identification and mitigation of any ethical issues and concerns related to the implementation of these systems are essential. To evaluate the ethical impact of the robots and deal with any problems found, an ongoing procedure of ethical impact assessment should be used [8].

Please refer to Appendix for the detailed ethics audit designed to evaluate the design, development, implementation, and assessment of autonomous drones used in public healthcare.

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APPENDIX A

ALTAI FRAMEWORK

The following Ethics Audit is based on the ALTAI framework and aims to ensure that the Killer Robots adhere to ethical principles and guidelines while maximizing their benefits. The audit takes into account the specific considerations and challenges associated with the use of autonomous drones in healthcare contexts.

- Is a defined governance framework in place for the creation and use of killer robots? Analyze whether there is a clear governance system in place for the creation and application of killer robots.
- Are specific people or groups in charge of making sure ethical factors are incorporated into the development process? Find out if there are specific people or groups in charge of handling ethical issues and keeping an eye on compliance.
- Exists a way to hold people or organizations responsible for any ethical transgressions or harm brought on by killer robots? In order to ensure ethical behavior and responsible decision-making, evaluate the accountability systems in place.

b) **Human Control and Decision-Making:** For the use of killer robots to be ethical and accountable, human control and decision-making are essential. Key factors include command responsibility, human accountability, accountability gap, meaningful human control, respect for human dignity and the right to life, unpredictability and reliability, and evidentiary obstacles. Establishing measures to ensure that those responsible for the creation and usage of killer robots are held accountable for any damage these systems may do is crucial.:

- Are there safeguards in place to guarantee that people have enough control over killer robots? Analyze the extent to which killer robots are under human control when they are in action.
- Are there precise rules and procedures for human intervention and judgment in urgent situations? Examine the systems in place to make sure that, if needed, human intervention is possible.
- The degree of human control over the system is determined and evaluated in what ways? Analyze the killer robots' decision-making processes and how they comport with moral standards like valuing human life and dignity.

c) **Transparency and Explainability:** Killer robot autonomy notwithstanding, people are still subject to legal liability for their deeds. Establishing methods to hold those responsible for the creation and usage of killer robots accountable for any damage the systems may cause is essential [9]. :

- Are the data sources, algorithms, and decision-making processes employed by killer robots transparent? Analyze the killer robots' functionality and design for transparency.
- Are there procedures in place to guarantee that killer robot decision-making is explicable and comprehensible to humans? Analyze the accessibility of data on the robots' decision-making algorithms, data sources, and sources of information.
- Can the system give thorough justifications for its choices and actions? Check to see if the robots can give humans-understandable justifications for their behaviors and choices.

d) **Unpredictability and Reliability:** In the world of killer robots, unpredictability and dependability are crucial factors. To ensure the responsible and ethical use of these systems, it is imperative to address their complexity, dependability, and accountability. Establishing measures to ensure that those responsible for the creation and usage of killer robots are held accountable for any damage these systems may do is crucial.:

- Are there steps being taken to address the concerns about killer robots' reliability and unpredictability? Analyze the steps taken to resolve the concerns about killer robots' unpredictability and dependability.
- How are the system's effectiveness and dependability in real-world situations tested and evaluated? Examine the

methods for testing and evaluating the robots' reliability and performance in real-world situations.

- Are backup systems or fail-safe procedures in place to reduce potential risks and failures? Check to see if there are any backup or fail-safe systems in place to reduce risks and failures.

e) **Compliance with International Humanitarian and Human Rights Law:** In the world of killer robots, adherence to international humanitarian and human rights legislation is essential. Key issues include adherence to IHL, resolving the absence of human traits, the responsibility gap, establishing legal restrictions, and ethical ramifications. To limit harm and safeguard human rights, it is crucial to make sure that killer robots are created, produced, and used in a way that complies with current legal frameworks. :

- Does the system abide by international humanitarian law and human rights legislation, including the distinction, proportionality, and precautionary principles? Assess the extent to which killer robots comply with ethical principles and legal frameworks, such as international humanitarian law and human rights. Evaluate the mechanisms in place to ensure compliance with relevant ethical guidelines and standards.
- Exist safeguards to make sure the system doesn't operate in violation of moral standards and legal guidelines? Determine if the robots are designed and implemented in a manner that respects the rights and well-being of individuals involved.

f) **Ethical Impact Assessment:** An ethical impact analysis is an important factor to take into account when discussing killer robots. Key issues include designing morally sound autonomous systems, upholding the dignity of the human person and the right to life, accountability discrepancies, legal and moral issues, and ethical impact analysis. To limit harm and defend human rights, it is crucial to make sure that killer robots are created, produced, and utilized in a way that complies with ethical standards and governing laws. :

- Has an evaluation of the ethical implications of the use of killer robots been done to identify and address any potential ethical hazards and concerns? Analyze the existence of a killer robot ethical effect assessment method.
- Exist continual monitoring and evaluation procedures to evaluate the system's ethical influence in practical situations? Analyze how any ethical hazards and concerns related to the deployment and use of these robots can be identified and mitigated.
- Exist established procedures to remedy any discovered ethical problems or unforeseen effects? Assessing the ethical impact of the robots and resolving any issues that are found may need ongoing monitoring and review methods.